

Some new 1-benzyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridylidenamino, dichlorophosphine

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Some new functionalized dichlorophosphines namely, 1-benzyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridineamino dichlorophosphines (3) have been synthesized by reactions of 2-amino-1-benzylpyridinium bromides (2) with PCl_3 and Et_3N . These compounds have been characterized by molecular weight determinations, melting point determinations, elemental analyses and on the basis of ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P NMR studies.

Functionalized dichlorophosphines are the important starting materials for the preparation of a variety of organophosphorus compounds¹. Schmidpeter *et al.*² have recently reported the synthesis, structural studies and reactions of several triarylphosphonium dichlorophosphinomethylides. Analogously, several interesting *N*-pyridinium dichlorophosphinomethylides have been obtained from the reaction of 1-alkylpyridinium bromides with phosphorus trichloride in the presence of triethylamine³. Some of these compounds have been found to undergo, 1,5-electrocyclization through the intermediacy of bis(*N*-pyridinium ylidyl) phosphonium chloride formed as a result of disproportionation of the former to give a new class of 2-phosphaindolizines which possess alkoxycarbonyl group both at 1- and 3-positions⁴.

Another important class of functionalized dichlorophosphines namely 1-alkyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridylidenamino dichlorophosphines and related compounds have been synthesized from the reaction of 1-alkyl-2-amino-pyridinium halides with phosphorus trichloride in the presence of triethylamine⁵⁻⁷. These compounds can act as precursors for annulated diazaphospholes if the former have an activated substituted methyl group at 1-position^{5,6}. Functionalized dichlorophosphines have been converted into a variety of organophosphorus compounds through electrophilic and nucleophilic substitution reactions⁸.

In view of these results it was planned to synthesize some new functionalized dichlorophosphines and the results are described in this article.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of 2-amino-1-benzylpyridinium bromides :

On stirring 2-aminopyridines (1) with equimolar amount of benzyl bromide in THF at RT, 1-benzyl-2-aminopyridinium bromides (2) are obtained in quantitative yield.

Scheme 1

The resulting compounds (2) are stable, high melting solids, soluble in chloroform and methylene chloride but insoluble in nonpolar solvents like ether and toluene. These pyridinium salts have been characterized on the basis of ^1H and ^{13}C NMR studies. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts of different signals and their assignments are given in Table 1.

Synthesis and characterization of 1-benzyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridylidenamino, dichlorophosphine (2) :

2-Amino-1-benzylpyridinium bromides (2) react with PCl_3 (1 equiv.) in the presence of Et_3N (2 equiv.) in benzene under nitrogen at RT to give 1-benzyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridylidenamino, dichlorophosphine (3).

Scheme 2

Table 1. Physical and spectral (^1H and ^{13}C NMR) data of 1-alkyl-2-aminopyridinium bromides (2)

Compd.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Yield (%)	M. p. (°C)	Solvent δ (ppm), J (Hz)	^1H NMR	^{13}C NMR δ (ppm)
2a	CH ₃	H	H	71	179–181	CDCl ₃ + DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆	2.23 (1H, s, CH ₃), 5.81 (2H, s, NCH ₂), 6.83 (1H, t, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.83, 5-H), 7.37 (5H, s, Ph), 7.59 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.83, 4-H), 7.77 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.34, 6-H), 8.26 (2H, s, NH ₂)	
2b	H	CH ₃	H	74	191–192	CDCl ₃	2.32 (3H, s, CH ₃), 5.85 (2H, s, NCH ₂), 6.70 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 9.85, 5-H), 7.55 (5H, s, Ph), 7.68 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.73 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.76, 6-H), 8.80 (2H, s, NH ₂)	21.4 (s, 4-CH ₃), 56.61 (s, NCH ₂), 114.85 (s, C-5), 115.47 (s, C-3), 128.23 (s, C- <i>o</i>), 128.77 (s, C- <i>p</i>), 129.04 (s, C- <i>m</i>), 132.02 (s, C- <i>i</i>), 137.60 (s, C-4), 153.80 (s, C-6), 154.07 (s, C-2)
2c	H	H	CH ₃	64	195–197	CDCl ₃ + DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆	2.16 (3H, s, CH ₃), 5.45 (2H, s, NCH ₂); 7.27 (5H, s, Ph), 7.51 (1H, dd, $^4J_{\text{HH}}$ 12.1, 4-H), 7.72 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.79 (1H, s, 6-H), 8.39 (2H, s, NH ₂).	–

The product has been isolated as cream colored crystalline sharp melting solid which is stable under dry nitrogen for some days but decomposes rapidly on exposure to atmosphere, particularly to moisture. They are soluble in chloroform, acetonitrile and methylene chloride but insoluble in nonpolar solvents. These compounds have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses and ^{31}P , ^1H and ^{13}C NMR studies.

^{31}P NMR : The ^{31}P NMR shift in the range δ 122–138 is well accordance with the reported values⁵. The structure is further confirmed by recording ^1H -coupled ^{31}P NMR spectrum of **3a** when no splitting of ^{31}P NMR signal is observed.

^1H NMR : In ^1H NMR spectrum of **3a**, a singlet at δ 5.42 assignable to *N*-methylene protons rules out the presence of dichlorophosphino moiety on the *N*-methylene group. Further, the signal of 2-amino group in the pyridinium salt at δ 8.56 is missing in the product thereby confirming the presence of dichlorophosphino moiety on nitrogen. The 3-H proton is highly deshielded and absorbs as a doublet at δ 8.01 ($^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 9.0 Hz). 4-H proton appears as added at δ 7.72 ($^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 9.0 Hz, 7.1 Hz; $^4J_{\text{HH}}$ 1.7 Hz; $^5J_{\text{PH}}$ 1.7 Hz) due to the vicinal coupling with 3-H and 5-H protons, as well as long range coupling with phosphorus. 5-H proton appears as a doublet at δ 6.73 ($^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 7.1 Hz, 6.6 Hz; $^4J_{\text{HH}}$ 1.7 Hz) due to

the vicinal coupling with 4-H and 6-H protons and long range coupling with 3-H proton. 6-H proton gives a doublet at δ 7.66 ($^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.6 Hz). *o*-H protons of benzene ring give a multiplet at δ 7.29 and *m*-, *p*-protons also give a multiplet in the range δ 7.34–7.40. The ^{31}P and ^1H NMR chemical shifts and their assignments are given in Table 2.

^{13}C NMR : The ^{13}C NMR spectra of **3a** have also been recorded. The C-2 carbon is highly deshielded and absorbs as a doublet at δ 155.8 ($^3J_{\text{PC}}$ 22.3 Hz). The *N*-methylene carbon gives a doublet at δ 155.5 with a low value of four bond coupling constant ($^4J_{\text{PC}}$ 1.4 Hz). The other ring carbons absorb in the expected region. The chemical shift values of different carbons and their assignments are given in Table 2.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out under dry nitrogen or argon atmosphere using the Schlenk technique. NMR spectra have been recorded on a Bruker ARX300 (^1H NMR at 300 MHz and ^{13}C NMR at 75.5 MHz) spectrometer or JEOL FX 90Q (^1H NMR at 89.55 MHz) spectrometer. The chemical shifts refer to 85% H_3PO_4 (taking external) or TMS as an internal standard.

Synthesis of 2-amino-1-benzylpyridinium bromides :
General procedure :

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 Table 2. Physical and spectral (^{31}P , ^1H and ^{13}C NMR) data of 1-benzyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridylidenamino, dichlorophosphine (3)

Compd.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	2			3			Elemental analysis (%)		
				Mol. formula (M. Wt.)	Yield (%)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	^{31}P δ (ppm)	^1H NMR δ (ppm), J (Hz)	^{13}C NMR δ (ppm), J (Hz)	Found/(calcd.)		
										C	H	N
3a	H	H	H	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ PCl ₂ (285.1)	52	97–99	137.7	5.42 (2H, s, NCH ₂), 6.73 (1H, ddd, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 7.1, 6.6, $^4J_{\text{HH}}$ 1.7, 5-H), 7.29 2H, m, 2-H), 7.34– 7.40 (3H, m, <i>m</i> -H, <i>p</i> - H), 7.66 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.6, 6-H), 7.72 (1H, dddd, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 9.0, 7.1, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 1.7, $^5J_{\text{PH}}$ 1.7, 4-H), 8.01 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 9.0, 3-H)	55.5 (d, $^4J_{\text{PC}}$ 1.4, NCH ₂), 113.2 (s, C-5), 121.4 (d, $^3J_{\text{PC}}$ 21.3, C-3), 128.5 (s, C- <i>o</i>), 128.8 (s, C- <i>p</i>), 129.2 (s, C- <i>m</i>), 134.4 (s, C- <i>i</i>), 138.7 (s, C-6, 140.5 (d, $^3J_{\text{PC}}$ 3.8, C-4), 155.8 (d, $^2J_{\text{PC}}$ 22.3, C-2)	50.51 (49.91)	3.88 (4.19)	9.83 (10.6)
3b	CH ₃	H	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ PCl ₂ (299.2)	40	93–95	128.0	2.74 (3H, s, CH ₃), 5.62 (2H, s, NCH ₂), 6.95 (1H, dd, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 7.0, 6.5, 5-H), 7.65 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 6.5, 4- H), 7.98 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 7.0, 6-H), 7.19– 9.26 (5H, bs, C ₆ H ₅)				
3c	H	CH ₃	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ PCl ₂ (299.2)	47	96–98	137.1	2.84 (3H, s, CH ₃), 5.58 (2H, s, NH ₂), 6.92 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 7.0, 5-H), 7.77 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.86 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 7.0, 6-H), 7.15– 7.28 (5H, bs, C ₆ H ₅)				
3d	H	H	CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ PCl ₂ (299.2)	51	101–103	134.3	2.68 (3H, s, CH ₃), 5.43 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.18–7.32 (5H, bs, C ₆ H ₅), 7.68 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 8.0, 3-H), 7.83 (1H, d, $^3J_{\text{HH}}$ 8.0, 4-H), 7.92 (1H, s, 6-H)				

To a solution of methyl substituted 2-amino pyridine (1) (0.025 mol) in a mixed solvent containing THF (60 ml) and diethylether (10 ml), a solution of benzyl bromide (3.6 g, 2.6 ml; 0.025 mol) in THF (10 ml) was added slowly at RT with continuous stirring. After stirring for 2 days, colourless to cream coloured solid separated which was filtered, washed with diethylether (2 × 30 ml) and dried under reduced pressure. The 2-amino-1-benzylpyridinium bromides (2) thus obtained in quantitative yields were used without further purification.

Synthesis of 1-benzyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridylidenamino, dichlorophosphine (3) : General procedure :

Substituted 2-aminopyridinium bromide (0.009 mol) was suspended in toluene (25 ml) and phosphorus trichloride (1.30 g, 0.8 ml; 0.009 mol) was added with stirring. A solution of triethylamine (1.93 g, 2.6 ml; 0.019 mol) in toluene (10 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for another 3–4 h. The formation of aminodichlorophosphine (3) was indicated by ^{31}P NMR

signal at δ 122–138. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with diethyl ether (2×50 ml). The ethereal extract was concentrated to about 10 ml and left in refrigerator when cream coloured solid separated which was filtered and dried *in vacuo*.

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